

Technical Paper

Sustainable soil improvement using marine-derived biopolymers: strength and durability perspectives

Runshen Wang^a, Hadi Fatehi^{b,c,*}, Dominic E.L. Ong^{b,c}, Jimmy Yu^c,
Ilhan Chang^d, Khosro Shabani^e

^a Key Laboratory of Geomechanics and Embankment Engineering of Ministry of Education, Hohai University, Nanjing 210024, China

^b Cities Research Institute, Griffith University, Nathan, QLD 4111, Australia

^c School of Engineering and Built Environment, Griffith University, Nathan, QLD 4111, Australia

^d Department of Civil System Engineering, Ajou University, the Republic of Korea

^e School of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Technology Sydney (UTS), Sydney, Australia

Received 3 August 2025; received in revised form 2 December 2025; accepted 27 December 2025

Available online 24 January 2026

Abstract

This study provides a comprehensive evaluation of marine biopolymers for sustainable soil stabilization. It offers critical insights for countries with abundant ocean resources to support the selection of suitable biopolymer for soil enhancement. The experimental program covers a wide range of mechanical and microstructural evaluations to support a broad understanding of biopolymer-treated soil behaviour. A range of marine biopolymers was tested with a specific focus on chitosan due to its distinct structure and bonding capability. The study focused on engineered kaolinite-sand mixtures, selected for their ability to represent complex and variable soil conditions commonly encountered in the field. Experimental variables such as biopolymer content, curing time, and soil composition were systematically controlled. Mechanical properties were assessed using UCS, and static and dynamic triaxial tests to determine shear strength and resilient modulus. Durability was assessed through five cycles of wetting and drying to replicate long-term environmental exposure. Results showed that biopolymer content and soil type significantly influenced strength development and water resistance. Chitosan achieved up to a tenfold increase in UCS, with substantial strength retention and low mass loss under cyclic conditions. Microstructural analysis using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) provided insights into the chemical bonding and physical interactions at the soil–biopolymer interface. A mechanical model was proposed to explain these interactions. Overall, the study demonstrates the potential of marine biopolymers as effective, ecofriendly alternatives to traditional chemical stabilizers, offering a sustainable solution for geotechnical engineering applications.

© 2026 Japanese Geotechnical Society. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Keywords: Biopolymer soil stabilization; Chitosan; Sustainable geotechnical solutions; Marine biopolymers; Triaxial behaviour

1. Introduction

From a construction perspective, problematic soils can pose significant challenges, and ground improvement techniques are essential to enhance the engineering properties of these soils and make them more suitable for construction applications. Soil improvement can be categorized into three main forms: mechanical, chemical, and biological stabilization (Chang et al., 2020; Samad et al., 2021).

* Corresponding author at: Cities Research Institute, Griffith University, Nathan, QLD 4111, Australia.

E-mail addresses: hadi.fatehiglab@griffithuni.edu.au, Fatehi.Hadi.324324@gmail.com, Hadi.fatehiglab@griffithuni.com.au (H. Fatehi), d.ong@griffith.edu.au (D.E.L. Ong), jimmy.yu@griffith.edu.au (J. Yu), ilhanchang@ajou.ac.kr (I. Chang), khosro.shabani@student.uts.edu.au (K. Shabani).

Mechanical methods involve physically changing the soil properties, such as compaction and the addition of gravel and sand to improve the load-bearing capacity and reduce settlement (Afrin 2017). Nanomaterials have gained attention in recent years as an innovative approach to soil stabilization. In addition, microbially induced calcium precipitation (MICP) is an emerging biological technique in which microorganisms facilitate the precipitation of calcite to enhance soil cohesion and reduce permeability (Bahrami et al., 2020; Kang et al., 2020; Mirazizi et al., 2023).

In the pursuit of a sustainable environment, natural biopolymers have recently been introduced, demonstrating tremendous potential in geotechnical operations and serving as an environmentally safe additives for soil remediation (Reddy and Varaprasad 2021, Mostafaei et al., 2024). These biopolymers are highly biodegradable and environmentally sustainable compared to the conventional additives. Numerous studies have investigated the use of various biopolymers, which can be categorized into three groups based on their origin: animal-based biopolymers (e.g., dextran, xanthan, and gellan gum), microorganism-based biopolymers (e.g., casein and chitosan), and plant-based biopolymers (e.g., guar gum, carrageenan, lignin, beta glucan, agar gum, and alginate) (Niaounakis 2015; Fatehi et al., 2021).

One of the most important sources of biopolymer production is the ocean, particularly from seafood waste and marine seeds (Sujatha and Saisree 2019; Fatehi et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2025). This can be advantageous for countries with extensive coastlines, such as India, Australia, the United States, and Canada. The most prevalent marine biopolymers with adhesive capability are sodium alginate, agar, carrageenan, and chitosan (Fatehi et al., 2021). Sodium alginate is produced using alginic acid, which is found in brown seaweeds (Afshar et al., 2020). Agar, a powerful gelling hydrocolloid, is derived from coastal red algae. Red seaweed is the source of carrageenan, an additive used to thicken, emulsify, and preserve foods and drinks (Kulkarni and Shaw 2015). The parent substance of chitosan, chitin, is a biopolymer found in many organisms, such as the exoskeletons of crustaceans (including shrimps, crayfish, krill, lobsters, and barnacles), mollusks (such as cuttlefish, octopus, clams, squid, oysters, and snails), and algae (including green/brown algae and diatoms) (Almajed et al., 2020; Ni et al., 2022; Shabani et al., 2022; Mehmood et al., 2025; Rasheed et al., 2025).

Marine biopolymers have demonstrated excellent performance in improving problematic soils across various fields of geotechnical engineering (Kang et al., 2019; Smitha et al., 2019; Smitha et al., 2021; Fatehi et al., 2024). Sodium alginate and agar were utilized as adhesive agents to different soil types and remarkably enhanced the strength of soils composed of various sand-kaolinite combinations (Fatehi et al., 2023). Moreover, Ni et al. explored the impact of using a combination of carrageenan and casein on the reinforcement of clayey soil, considering

biodeterioration. Their findings indicated that the carrageenan-casein mixture resulted in higher compressive strength than using carrageenan or casein alone, due to the creation of a three-dimensional gel network (Ni et al., 2022). The use of shrimp-derived chitosan for the reinforcement of silt with low plasticity was investigated by assessing its effects on hydraulic conductivity, pH, strength, compaction, and consolidation properties. Their study concluded that the formation of biopolymer threads within the soil matrix bridged the voids, resulting in a stiffer soil structure with increased strength and reduced hydraulic conductivity. (Kannan and Sujatha 2023).

It was recently found that biopolymer-stabilized earthen construction materials treated with 2.5% chitosan exhibited a 27% increase in average compressive strength and an 11% improvement in average flexural strength compared to control samples containing 8% cement. Stabilized soft clays exposed to freeze–thaw cycles were investigated using chitosan, and it was found to be highly effective in resisting freeze–thaw damage (Hataf et al., 2018; Shariatmadari et al., 2020; Ghadir et al., 2022). Low-cohesion soil specimens treated with two chitosan solutions were tested under dynamic and cyclic loading to determine the soil shear modulus in relation to strain values. It was demonstrated that even relatively low concentrations of chitosan (1.5%) significantly enhanced the shear modulus of medium-grained materials. The findings further indicated that chitosan solutions could serve as highly effective, environmentally friendly, and temporary stabilizers for short-term geotechnical structures, such as working platforms. To maximize productivity, the wet-mixing method for preparing the chitosan–soil mixture was identified as the most effective approach, as it ensures a uniform blend of the biopolymer with the soil and optimizes chitosan–soil particle interactions. This method has been widely adopted in biopolymer soil-stabilization studies for its consistency and efficiency (Fatehi et al., 2023; Fatehi et al., 2024; Rasheed et al., 2025; Wang et al., 2025).

Despite increasing attention to marine biopolymers for soil stabilization, most existing studies have focused on limited aspects of individual biopolymers without fully addressing the combined effects of mechanical, chemical, and environmental factors across different materials. This study adopts an integrated approach, combining strength and durability testing with microstructural and chemical characterization to obtain a more complete understanding of biopolymer-soil interaction. In particular, dynamic tri-axial tests were used to determine the resilient modulus, offering deeper insight into mechanical performance under cyclic loading. The experimental program includes UCS testing, FTIR analysis, the SEM imaging, and the development of a chemical interaction model to understand the bonding mechanisms involved. Initial tests were conducted to identify optimal biopolymer content and curing conditions, followed by a detailed evaluation of engineered kaolinite-sand mixtures. Durability was assessed through five wetting–drying cycles. The study also provides a

comparative analysis of four marine biopolymers—agar gum, sodium alginate, carrageenan, and chitosan—under identical conditions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Soil

Kaolinite silt was obtained from Kaolin Malaysia, a company specializing in mining products. Aluminum silicate is the primary chemical component of the kaolinite silt, with minor constituents such as K_2O and Fe_2O_3 . The composition of the soil, as determined by grain size distribution and hydrometer tests, classifies it as high-plasticity kaolinite silt (MH) with a Skempton activity value of 0.77, according to the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS) (Table 1). River sand (RS) was sourced from a building site in Gold Coast, Australia, and is classified as poorly graded sand (SP) by the USCS (D6913-04 2009, D6913/D6913M-17 2017).

The gradation analysis of both the sand and kaolinite silt is illustrated in Fig. 1. Kaolinite silt and poorly graded sand are selected for mixing to evaluate the effect of soil type on the performance of chitosan-treated soils. By creating various sand-kaolinite mixtures, the study aims to assess how different soil compositions influence the stabilization process and the resulting soil properties, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of chitosan's effectiveness across diverse soil types.

2.2. Chitosan

Countries such as the USA, Japan, Canada, China, and Norway typically utilize by-products from crustacean fishing for chitin production. The main industrial source for chitosan extraction is the shells of crabs, prawns, and lob-

Table 1
Geotechnical properties of kaolinite silt and sand.

Property	Kaolinite Silt	Sand
Particle size / fractions		
Sand fraction (%)	0.88	—
Silt fraction (%)	78.00	—
Clay fraction (%)	21.12	—
D50 (mm)	—	0.49
Plasticity / index properties		
Liquid limit, LL (%)	62	—
Plastic limit, PL (%)	46	—
Plasticity index, PI (%)	16	—
Activity (PI / Clay content)	0.77	—
Classification / density		
USCS	MH	SP
Minimum void ratio, e_{min}	—	0.61
Maximum void ratio, e_{max}	—	0.76
Coefficient of uniformity, C_u	—	2.77
Coefficient of curvature, C_c	—	0.91
Specific gravity, G_s	—	2.63
Particle shape	—	Round

Fig. 1. Particle size distribution of kaolinite silt and sand.

sters. (Hamdi et al., 2017). Annually, the production of chitin and its derivatives is estimated to be around 100 million tons (Jafari et al., 2012). Chitin is insoluble in water and most organic acids because of its extensive hydrogen bonding (Izumi et al., 2015). In this study, chitosan was purchased from Chemsupply, with CAS No. 9012-76-4. Table 2 present detailed properties of the chitosan biopolymer.

2.3. Sample preparation

The following steps were taken to prepare the biopolymer solution. First, acetic acid with the concentration of 1% was prepared by dissolving required amount of glacial acetic acid in distilled water. Then, the solution was heated up to 80 °C and the required amount of chitosan powder was blended with the acetic acid solution. Finally, the solution was shaken until a uniform solution was obtained, ensuring that the concentration was low enough for complete dissolution of the biopolymer. The soil was then uniformly mixed with the solution for ten minutes after being oven-dried at 105 °C for 24 h. A small sample was collected and oven-dried to determine the moisture content. The remaining mixture was stored in a sealed bag for one day to allow uniform moisture distribution.

To produce consistent samples using the hydraulic jack in line with ASTM D4609 and ASTM D2850, a mould was specifically developed and assembled (D2850-23, D4609). The cylindrical stainless-steel tube that made up the bulk of the mould had two wings attached to the sides. The other parts involved a square plate of stainless steel, a cap, and both short and long hammers, and the mould cylinder had a diameter of 50 mm and a height of 200 mm, and the final sample height to ratio diameter was always kept between 2 and 2.2. The produced mixture was poured into the mould after lubricating the surfaces of

Table 2
Properties of chitosan biopolymer.

Product name	Chitosan
Form	Solid
Chemical formula	$C_{18}H_{35}N_3O_{13}$
Appearance	Faint Beige to Beige
Melting point	> 290 °C
Solubility in Water	insoluble in water and organic solvent, soluble in dilute aqueous acidic solution (pH < 6.5)
pH	6.5 – 7.5

the cap, short hammer, and inner wall of the tube. The sample was then compacted using the hydraulic jack in one layer after the mould position was adjusted using the square plate. The compaction load was applied until the soil reached the maximum density as obtained by the compaction test, corresponding to a relative density greater than 90%. After compaction, the samples were removed and subsequently cured in a controlled environment with a temperature of 23 °C and humidity ranging from 50 to 60%. To account for potential dimensional changes, the diameter and height of specimens were recorded immediately after sample preparation as well as when dried. No significant changes were observed; only the final dimensions were used for the analysis.

2.4. Experimental program

Compaction, UCS, static and dynamic triaxial tests, as well as FTIR and SEM analyses, were carried out to assess the effect of the biopolymer on the engineering parameters of the soil. The purpose of the compaction test was to obtain the maximum dry densities and optimum moisture contents to calculate the amount of soil and water for sample preparation. The mechanical characteristics of the biopolymer-treated soil (BPTS) were assessed using UCS and triaxial tests, and the interaction between the biopolymer and soil was microstructurally described using FTIR and SEM images. Table 3 contains the complete experimental plan for this study.

A labelling system is used to distinguish different specimens and consists of four sections: K (for kaolinite), a number (0–4), S (for sand), and a number (0 to 4). For example, K3S1 denotes a sand-kaolinite mixture that

contains 75% kaolinite and 25% sand, where the numbers indicate the proportion of each component in increments of 25%.

Various sand-kaolinite combinations were prepared using dry sand and kaolinite to explore the impact of soil type on the strength of biopolymer treated soil. These combinations are listed in Table 4. The samples were made using maximum dry density and optimum moisture content in line with ASTM D698-12 (D698-12). To achieve a homogeneous biopolymer solution, 12.86% of optimal moisture content for K1S3 was insufficient, therefore 15% of water content was considered (Fatehi et al., 2023).

2.4.1. Unconfined compression strength test

In line with ASTM D2166, Universal Testing Machine was used to measure the compressive strength. The moisture and biopolymer contents, curing time, soil type influence, and durability were among the factors evaluated using the UCS tests (ASTM 2006). The machine automatically monitored and recorded the stress–strain behaviour as the axial strain rate increased from 1%/min (1 mm/min) to 7%. The average result of three samples that were tested for each condition served as the unconfined compression strength.

2.4.2. Triaxial tests

A series of triaxial tests were conducted on natural and treated samples. The same preparation conditions as the UCS test were used for the triaxial samples, and then cured in a special room with carefully controlled conditions. In accordance with ASTM D7181, the samples were tested under consolidated undrained (CU) triaxial test (D7181-20).

The GDS Enterprise Level Dynamic Triaxial Testing System (ELDYN), as shown in Fig. 2, was employed for the triaxial testing. Samples were mounted on a bottom plate, which was topped with a rubber membrane. Porous stones were placed below and above to prevent contact with the chamber fluid. The setup was connected to a triaxial apparatus that was computer-controlled. To measure the axial strain a linear variable differential transformer was attached externally to the top of the chamber.

A set of static and dynamic triaxial tests were performed to evaluate the performance of chitosan in K1S3 soil samples. Initial confining pressure for all samples was kept

Table 3
Experimental program.

Test type	Biopolymer content (%)	Curing time (days)	Soil type	No. of wet-dry cycles
UCS	0, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5	14	K4S0, K1S3	–
	0, 0.5	0, 1, 3, 7, 14, 28	K4S0, K1S3	–
	0, 0.5	14	K4S0, K3S1, K2S2, K1S3, K0S4	–
	0, 0.5	14	K1S3	0, 1, 2, 3, 5
Static Triaxial	0, 0.5	14	K4S0, K1S3	–
Cyclic triaxial		14	K4S0, K1S3	–
FTIR		14	K1S3	–
SEM		14	K4S0, K1S3, K0S4	–

Table 4
Sand-kaolinite mixtures properties.

Label	Soil (%)			Optimum moisture content (%)	Maximum dry density (gr/cm ³)
	Sand	Silt	Clay		
K4S0	0	80	20	35.13	1.37
K3S1	25	60	15	29.88	1.57
K2S2	50	40	10	20.25	1.75
K1S3	75	20	5	12.86	2.04
K0S4	100	0	0	16.75	1.83

as 100 kPa. Static triaxial tests were performed on both dry and saturated samples. Saturation was achieved by applying back pressure from the bottom, allowing air in the pores to dissolve into the deaired water. Throughout the saturation process, an effective stress of 20 kPa was maintained. Saturation persisted until the B value exceeded 95%, indicating the successful saturation. As the samples were prepared using a hydraulic jack, minimal consolidation was anticipated during the consolidation stage. To confirm the absence of significant consolidation, a brief consolidation under 50 kPa pressure was applied as an additional precautionary measure. The applied strain rate at the shearing stage was 0.1 mm/min.

Cyclic triaxial tests were also conducted under stress control conditions. The saturation and consolidation stages were performed as in the static tests. The applied deviatoric stress was applied at 40 and 100 kPa for 5000 cycles. The load type was a half-sine waveform with a frequency of 1 Hz.

2.4.3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images

To investigate the structure and microscopic interaction of the biopolymer and soil, SEM images were collected. For this purpose, untreated (kaolinite, sand, and K1S3) and treated soil samples were employed. To ensure dryness, the samples were stored in the oven at 35 °C for one day. Afterwards, carbon conductive tabs were used to attach them to an SEM mount. Samples were coated with carbon

paint to ensure electrical conductivity and subsequently wrapped with conductive tape. For specimen observation, a Zeiss Sigma VP Field Emission Scanning *Electron Microscope* (Oberkochen, Germany) was employed.

2.4.4. Attenuated total reflectance fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy

ATR-FTIR analysis was performed on the soil samples using a Bruker Tensor27 spectrometer in the 400–4000 cm⁻¹ range to identify the functional groups present in various soil samples. The potassium bromide (KBr) disc method was employed to prepare the soil samples for examination at a ratio of 100:1 (KBr to soil).

3. Results

3.1. Unconfined compression strength (UCS) test

3.1.1. Particle size effect

Fig. 3 displays the UCS test results for various sand-kaolinite mixtures treated with 0.5% of chitosan and cured for 14 days at 23 °C and humidity of 50 – 60%. Sand content varies in sand-kaolinite combinations by 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 percent (denoted as K4S0, K3S1, K2S2, K1S3, and K0S4, respectively). Since the moisture content was less than 1% in every sample, the effect of moisture can be neglected. For K0S4 (pure sand), it was not feasible to prepare UCS samples due to the very low cohesion (considered zero). Therefore, the data for untreated K0S4 was excluded from Fig. 3.

According to Fig. 3a, K1S3 had the greatest compressive strength among soil combinations tested in both untreated and treated states. The primary reason for the high UCS of soil K1S3 is its well-graded size distribution, as the kaolinite particles fill the voids between the sand particles. As a result of the particles interlocking, the mixture can form a denser soil structure. The mixtures showed a significant improvement in UCS when treated with 0.5% biopolymer compared with untreated samples. Kaolinite (K4S0) treated with chitosan (CH) had the least strength improvement, indicating that it is the least responsive to biopolymer treatment. whereas treated K1S3 displayed the greatest UCS strength improvement, showing that chitosan was highly effective for K1S3. Therefore, these two soil types (K1S3 and K4S0) were selected for subsequent experiments.

Fig. 2. Triaxial testing system and a sample used for the dynamic test.

Fig. 3. UCS test results for different treated and untreated soil types.

Additionally, Fig. 3b presents the elastic modulus for different soil types. As shown, it follows a trend similar to the compressive strength, which reflects the stiffness of the soil. A higher elasticity modulus indicates a stiffer material, which can sustain higher loads with limited deformation (Ohadian, Khayat et al. 2024). K1S3 exhibited the highest elasticity modulus in both untreated and treated conditions, and similar to its UCS behavior, this behavior is attributed to its well-graded particle distribution and strong interlocking. Overall, chitosan treatment considerably enhanced the stiffness of soil for all soil types, while the magnitude of improvement was strongly dependent on soil composition and gradation.

3.1.2. Biopolymer content

Fig. 4 displays the compressive strength test results for the natural and chitosan-treated samples with chitosan concentrations (0, 0.25, 0.5, 1, and 1.5%). The treated specimens were maintained for two weeks under controlled conditions. The initial moisture contents of K4S0 and K1S3 samples were 35% and 15%, respectively (Fatehi et al., 2024).

According to Fig. 4, the UCS values for untreated soils were 316 kPa for K4S0 and 406 kPa for K1S3. The results show that adding biopolymer up to 1% significantly improves the compressive strength for both soils. While a slight decrease occurred for K1S3 treated with 1.5% chitosan, the increasing trend for treated K4S0 samples continued with further biopolymer addition. The compressive strength of treated K1S3 peaked at 4500 kPa, at 1% biopolymer content. The strength reduction after peak for treated K1S3 is caused by excessive biopolymer gel formation beyond the optimal concentration needed for particle bonding. The excess gel produces a lubrication effect that reduces the particle bonding effectiveness. Consequently, the excess gel allows for greater grain movement so that less compressive strength was reduced.

Similar to the compressive strength, the elastic modulus increased as the biopolymer content increased. As anticipated, the treated K1S3 samples exhibited higher elastic modulus values than the treated K4S0 samples. Sand and kaolinite gained higher compressive strength and stiffness due to the cementing effect of the biopolymer. Biopolymers bond with the soils through several mechanisms, including (a) hydrogen bonding between the functional groups of the biopolymers and the hydroxylated surfaces of kaolinite, (b) electrostatic interactions among the charged surfaces of biopolymers and kaolinite, and (c) hydrophobic interactions. Additionally, by distributing polymer chains throughout the soil voids and covering the surfaces of sand particles, a robust and well-integrated film network is created throughout the treated soil matrix, enhancing the mechanical resistance and limiting soil particle movement.

3.1.3. Curing time

After 1, 3, 7, 14, and 28 days of curing samples in a controlled environment, the impact of dehydration time on the strength of BPTS (K4S0 and K1S3) was examined. The UCS test results for both natural and 0.5% chitosan-treated soils are shown in Fig. 5.

Effectiveness of chitosan treatment was evident from the very early phases of dehydration (0 days of curing) since the strength values increased markedly, from 265 kPa to 820 kPa and from 275 kPa to 336 kPa for K1S3 and K4S0, respectively. The compressive strength continued to increase over time. More than 90% of the compressive strength for both treated K1S3 and K4S0 was achieved within the first 14 days of dehydration. Afterward, the strength increased slightly until day 28. As a result, the optimal dehydration period in following stages of the study was chosen as 14 days.

Fig. 4. Compressive strength and elasticity modulus for different biopolymer contents.

Fig. 5. Unconfined compressive strength over time for treated and untreated K4S0 and K1S3.

3.1.4. Durability by wet-dry cycle

Three specimens were prepared for each condition using natural and treated K1S3 with 0.5% chitosan for the durability test. Each sample was placed in a 55 mm-diameter plastic tube, allowing free movement of soil particles and biopolymer. Specimens were soaked in water for 24 h before being dried for 14 days. The 24-hour wetting time

was sufficient to simulate the immersion cycle. Saturation for all samples was measured less than an hour, the remaining 23 h were to ensure samples are exposed to adequate moisture absorption. The 14-day dehydration period was required to reach a moisture content of below 1%, as it determined in the previous section. The samples were subjected to up to five wetting and drying cycles, with testing

occurring after each cycle (cycles 0, 1, 2, 3, and 5). Fig. 6 shows examples of the samples from cycles 1 to 5.

Fig. 7 shows the UCS and elastic modulus of K1S3 specimens after 1, 2, 3, and 5 cycles of wetting and drying (cured for 14 days). The strength and elastic modulus of the samples were significantly lowered by wetting and drying. After five cycles, pure soil samples lost around 78% of their original strength, whereas treated samples responded better. K1S3 treated with chitosan performed far better than untreated K1S3, losing only 33% of its original strength after five wet-dry cycles. Water absorbed into the soil pores increases pore pressure, which weakens untreated soil and reduced the soil strength. While soaking in water decreases strength in biopolymer-treated soils, some polymer-soil bonds are re-established upon drying. Consequently, fewer soil grains detached from the soil matrix. Moreover, biopolymer-treated samples experienced a slight decrease in elastic modulus, consistent with the UCS results. Chitosan, as a non-soluble biopolymer, helps maintain the structure of the soil matrix and reduce shrinkage due to its resistance during water exposure. Thus, chitosan reduces the extent of soil strain softening by preserving the soil structure during wet-dry cycles.

Fig. 8 displays the mass loss of the samples during the durability test. After five wet-dry cycles, the mass loss associated with untreated samples is significantly greater than that of treated ones. The mass loss for each sample was calculated by measuring the initial dry mass before wetting–drying cycles and its dry mass after each subsequent cycle, once completely dried. Mass loss was calculated as the difference between the initial and final dry masses.

For instance, untreated samples lost 7.63% of their mass after five wet-dry cycles, but treated samples lost less than 0.5% of their mass. The cross-section may decrease due to

mass reduction, increasing the stress on the particles and possibly reducing the compressive strength. Additionally, when the samples are soaked, biopolymers get exposed to water, leading to the hydrated gel fibrils separating from the primary matrix. Because of moisture loss throughout the subsequent dehydration cycle, the detached film partially reattaches to the soil matrix, though a small portion of the original structure is not fully restored after each cycle. Decreased gel elastic modulus, decreased gel density, and a greater maximum strain are the consequences of this cyclic deterioration. This explains why treated soils gradually lose strength during wet-dry cycles, rather than experiencing sudden failure as in lime- or cement-treated soils (Fatehi et al., 2023).

3.2. Triaxial test

The shear strength of the soil was assessed by performing a set of static and dynamic triaxial tests for both treated and untreated samples. Effective confining stress was maintained at 100 kPa for all samples. Static tests were performed on the dry and saturated samples of K1S3 in untreated and treated (with 0.5% of chitosan and cured at 23 °C and 50–60% humidity) states. The shear rate of 0.1 mm/min was applied in the shearing stage of the test. In addition, the behaviour of samples was tested under cyclic loading using a stress-controlled test. The applied deviatoric stresses were 40 kPa and 100 kPa.

One of the obstacles to using biopolymers as a stabilising agent is their solubility in natural water. Therefore, the static triaxial tests were performed on the dry and saturated samples to evaluate the effect of saturation on the chitosan-treated soil. Fig. 9 presents the behaviour of the samples in CU tests. It is evident that chitosan-treated soil

Fig. 6. Samples pictures during wet-dry cycles. a) untreated K1S3, and b) treated K1S3.

Fig. 7. Mechanical strength of treated and untreated soil after exposure to wetting and drying cycles.

Fig. 8. Mass loss of soil specimens with repetitive wet-dry cycles.

performed significantly better to untreated soil regardless of the test condition. However, saturation negatively affected both sets of samples. K1S3 lost more than 40% of its strength (from 560 kPa to 332 kPa), while this reduction was less than 16% for the treated soil in terms of maximum deviatoric strength. According to the stress-strain graph, when saturated, the treated sample experienced a brittle failure with a peak strength of 2172 kPa and residual strength of around 1550 kPa.

In this study, cyclic triaxial tests were conducted on untreated and chitosan-treated K1S3 soil to investigate

the influence of chitosan biopolymer on the soil's behaviour under dynamic loading conditions. Prior to testing, samples were saturated for two days by applying back pressure, ensuring complete removal of air from the soil pores. The load amplitudes for the cyclic tests were determined based on static CU test results, specifically 10 and 25 percent of the maximum deviatoric strength of untreated K1S3 soil. These two different deviatoric load amplitudes were 30 kPa and 80 kPa, with a cyclic frequency of 1 Hz, and a total of 5000 cycles.

Fig. 10 illustrates the accumulated strain of the samples after 5000 cycles. Under 30 kPa, untreated K1S3 soil exhibited a permanent deformation of approximately 0.1%. In contrast, chitosan-treated K1S3 showed nearly negligible permanent deformation, indicating the favourable influence of chitosan in reducing soil deformation under cyclic loading. When subjected to an 80 kPa deviatoric load amplitude, untreated K1S3 soil experienced a drastic deformation, reaching more than 5% strain over less than 1000 cycles of loading. Conversely, the accumulated strain for the chitosan-treated soil remained below 0.1% even after 5000 cycles. These results highlight the effectiveness of chitosan treatment in enhancing the soil's resistance to deformation under dynamic loading conditions.

Resilient modulus (M_r) is a key parameter for the stiffness assessment of base and subbase materials. Resilient modulus refers to a material's ability to withstand and recover from deformation under varying load and environmental conditions, often used to assess the performance of flexible pavements in transportation engineering. M_r is calculated as the ratio between cyclic deviatoric stress (σ_d) and the elastic strain (ϵ_e) during dynamic loading. Elastic strain

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. Static consolidated undrained triaxial test results. a) stress–strain behaviour, b) maximum deviatoric stress.

is calculated as the difference between the total strain (ε_t) and the plastic strain (ε_p). The amount of resilient modulus is determined by the mean value of the elastic strain in the last 50 cycles of each test ($\varepsilon_{e,avg}$) (Santa 1994; Mousa et al. 2017; Arab et al. 2019).

$$M_r = \frac{\sigma_d}{\varepsilon_{e,avg}}$$

Fig. 11 represents the M_r of untreated K1S3 and chitosan-treated K1S3 under the deviatoric loads of 30 kPa and 80 kPa. As seen, the treated soil yields considerably higher M_r than the untreated soil in both conditions. As expected, the higher the applied load, the higher the resulting M_r . It is important to note that the samples were

fully saturated during the experiments, showing that the chitosan treatment remains effective even when dealing with water. This indicates that the chitosan treatment has strong potential in enhancing soil performance for pavements.

3.3. Microstructure and interaction models

This section describes the interactions that result in the development of kaolinite-biopolymer and sand-biopolymer composites. SEM images taken of untreated and treated samples (with 0.5% chitosan) are shown in Fig. 12. The images show that biopolymer films covered the grains and filled the voids in the soil mass to bridge particles through multiple mechanisms. Different interactions can be inferred depending on the type of soil, as described in the following sections.

3.3.1. Kaolinite/chitosan

Chitosan, a deacetylated form of chitin, is widely used due to its active functional groups including amine ($-\text{NH}_2$), hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$), and ketone ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$). The presence of ketone groups in the chitosan structure indicates the persistence of some acetyl groups. These functional groups in the chitosan structure are potentially active sites to establish effective hydrogen bonding with kaolinite particles bearing surface hydroxyl groups (aluminols) as shown in Fig. 13. Additionally, as a cationic polymer, chitosan interacts with negatively charged kaolinite platelets via Coulombic attraction. This electrostatic interaction contributes to the overall binding mechanism between chitosan and kaolinite particles.

Kaolinite platelets are generally considered to have negative surface charges due to isomorphous substitution, including those on the basal surfaces. As a result, electrostatic interactions are expected to dominate the adsorption of chitosan. In addition, other weak non-electrostatic forces, such as van der Waals interactions between the siloxane basal plane and the carbon backbone of chitosan might also contribute to the overall binding especially in areas with relatively low charge density (Gupta and Miller 2010; Kumar et al., 2017; Li et al., 2023).

Coulombic attraction and electrostatic interactions are key mechanisms contributing to the effective stabilization of soil by chitosan. Our findings are also consistent with previous studies where other biopolymers and nanomaterials enhanced soil mechanical properties (Kang and Bate, 2016; Fatehi et al., 2024; Khayat and Nasiri, 2024; Ohadian, Khayat et al. 2024).

3.3.2. Sand/chitosan composites

To outline the interactions involved in forming a river sand-chitosan (RS/chitosan) composite, i.e., the functional groups and charge characteristics of both components must first be examined. Overall, both chitosan and RS carry no significant net charge on their structures. However, depending on the pH of the medium, chitosan can

Fig. 10. Cyclic behaviour (accumulated strain) of untreated and treated K1S3.

Fig. 11. Resilient Modulus (M_r) of untreated and chitosan-treated K1S3.

become protonated at low pH and carry a positive charge. Moreover, since high pH conditions were not used during composite preparation, and the composite was examined

in its dry state, the electric charge parameter was not considered dominant. Two dominant driving forces govern the formation of RS/chitosan composite:

Fig. 12. SEM images for untreated and treated samples, a) K4S0, b) K1S3, c) treated K4S0, d) treated K1S3, and e) treated K0S4.

Fig. 13. Interaction of chitosan with kaolinite soil.

(1) The interfacial mechanical interaction between RS and chitosan polymer chains is a dominant driving force in their composite formation. A driving force in the successful formation of RS/chitosan composites is the mechanical interlocking created when chitosan coats the sand particles. Chitosan polymer chains surround the sand grains and, as a cohesive framework, increase the mechanical strength of the composite compared to their pure state as represented in Fig. 14.

(2) Most polymer chains exhibit hydrophobic tendencies due to their hydrocarbon backbones, and the generally non-polar surface characteristics of many mineral particles, hydrophobic such as sand and clay, one of the dominant interaction mechanisms in polymer–mineral composites is hydrophobic interaction.

There might also be hydrogen interactions. Due to the small number of active hydroxyl groups on RS particles compared to kaolinite, the potential hydrogen bonding

Fig. 14. Interaction of Chitosan and sand.

between chitosan and sand is expected to be much lower than that between kaolinite and chitosan.

3.4. FTIR spectra

ATR-FTIR spectra of untreated and chitosan-treated K1S3 are shown in Fig. 15. The ATR-FTIR spectrum of K1S3 showed four characteristic absorption bands at around 3700, 3670, 3650, and 3620 cm^{-1} correspond to stretching vibrations of $-\text{OH}$ groups indicating an ordered structure of kaolinite [1]. The spectrum of the treated sample also shows additional bands that are consistent with the presence of chitosan functional groups in the material. The three higher-wavenumber FTIR absorption bands are attributed to the inner surface $-\text{OH}$ (outer $-\text{OH}$), whereas the band at 3620 cm^{-1} is assigned to the inner $-\text{OH}$ [2]. The absorption bands in the 1089–1006 cm^{-1} range, with a peak at 1033 cm^{-1} are attributed to the asymmetric stretching mode of the $\text{Si}-\text{O}$ groups. The presence of absorption bands at around 794, 699, and 533 cm^{-1} is assigned to vibrations of $\text{Si}-\text{O}-\text{Al}$ group.

Also, ATR-FTIR frequency at the 910 cm^{-1} is related to the vibration of $\text{Al}-\text{OH}$ bond. ATR-FTIR spectrum of treated K1S3 (K1S3-Ch) showed all the above mentioned bands, which indicate the presence of kaolinite in its structure. However, when compared with the ATR-FTIR spectrum of the untreated sample, the treated K1S3 composite reveals new absorption bands in the wavenumber (cm^{-1}) regions around 2905–2865 cm^{-1} (C–H asymmetrical and symmetrical stretching), 1650 cm^{-1} (C=O, stretching), 1595 cm^{-1} (N–H, deformation), 1411 cm^{-1} (C–H, symmet-

ric bending vibration), and 1170–930 cm^{-1} (overlapped, C–O stretching), indicating the existence of the organic moiety (chitosan) in the composite structure. These observations indicate the incorporation of chitosan within the treated material; however, they FTIR alone in not sufficient to confirm the specific nature of interactions between chitosan and soil minerals.

4. Discussion

In this section, chitosan (CH) is compared to other marine biopolymers including sodium alginate (SA), agar gum (AG) and carrageenan (CA) and their various properties are examined. Because xanthan gum (XA) is widely used in this field, it is employed as a benchmark in these comparisons. All biopolymers are tested under the same experimental conditions.

4.1. Biopolymer content

Fig. 16 demonstrates the effect of different biopolymer contents on the UCS of soil (K1S3) treated with biopolymers including chitosan, sodium alginate, agar gum, carrageenan, and xanthan gum. The samples were cured for 14 days, and the results indicate chitosan outperformed other biopolymers at all tested concentrations (0.25%, 0.5%, 1%, 1.5%). The strength increase followed a similar trend for all biopolymer. The compressive strength of the soil significantly increased up to the 0.5% of biopolymer, after which further additions were less effective up to 1%,

Fig. 15. FTIR characterization for untreated and treated K1S3.

Fig. 16. Different biopolymers strength enhancement in terms of biopolymer content for K1S3 soil (Fatehi et al., 2023, Fatehi et al., 2024).

and at 1.5%, no significant improvement was observed. Overall, chitosan performed significantly better in all biopolymer contents. It was most effective at 1%, increasing soil strength by approximately 10-fold.

4.2. Soil type effect

Fig. 17 shows the results of the UCS test for different sand-kaolinite combinations treated with 0.5% of various

Fig. 17. Effect of various biopolymers on different soil types (Fatehi et al., 2023, Fatehi et al., 2024).

biopolymers and treated for 14 days. Among untreated soils, K1S3 exhibited the highest UCS compared to other soil types, K4S0, K3S1, K2S2, and K0S4. For fine-

graded soils, carrageenan had a greater enhancing effect than other biopolymers, causing a greater increase in UCS values for K4S0 and K3S1. For other soil types, chi-

(a)

(b)

Fig. 18. Comparison of the durability of K1S3 treated with different marine biopolymers. a) UCS, b) UCS reduction ratio, and c) mass loss of the samples after each cycle (Fatehi et al., 2023, Fatehi et al., 2024).

(c)

Fig 18. (continued)

tosan performed better compared to other marine biopolymers, especially in the case of K1S3, which chitosan treatment increased the UCS value by more than ninefold. Overall, chitosan exhibited a more consistent UCS enhancement compared to other biopolymers.

4.3. Durability

The UCS samples of untreated and K1S3 treated with various biopolymers were cured for 14 days and subjected to 5 cycles of wetting and drying, and the corresponding results are shown in Fig. 18 (Ayeldeen et al., 2018). After each cycle, chitosan-treated K1S3 exhibited the highest UCS value. However, the xanthan-treated soil has been the most durable composite as it exhibited the smallest UCS reduction rate. Furthermore, the chitosan-treated K1S3 showed the lowest mass loss among all biopolymers after each cycle. Consequently, considering its superior UCS and the least mass loss, chitosan biopolymer emerges as a favourable choice among marine biopolymers for effective soil improvement applications.

4.4. Triaxial behaviour

The results of the CD static triaxial tests for chitosan-treated soil are compared with the performance of other

biopolymers. Table 5 displays the shear parameters obtained from the CD triaxial test for untreated and biopolymer-treated K4S0 and K1S3 with 0.5% chitosan, carrageenan and xanthan. The results demonstrate a notable enhancement in the shear strength of both K4S0 and K1S3 soils after biopolymer incorporation. The initial cohesion (C') values for untreated K4S0 and K1S3 soils were recorded at 70 kPa and 60 kPa, respectively. However, the application of biopolymer treatment led to substantial increase in C' and ϕ' for both soil types. For instance, carrageenan treatment elevated the cohesion to 350 kPa for K4S0 and to 440 kPa for K1S3, while chitosan significantly raised the cohesion to 192 kPa and 480 kPa for

Table 5
Summary of the results of the triaxial test (Fatehi et al., 2023, Fatehi et al., 2024).

ID	Biopolymer Type	Biopolymer Content	C'	ϕ'
K4S0	–	–	70	23.76
K4S0-Car	Car	0.5	350	24.63
K4S0-Xa	Xanthan	0.5	95	33.2
K4S0-CH	Chitosan	0.5	192	34.58
K1S3	–	–	60	36.42
K1S3-Car	Car	0.5	440	38.91
K1S3-Xa	Xanthan	0.5	495	36.71
K1S3-CH	Chitosan	0.5	480	43.64

K4S0 and K1S3, respectively. Similarly, xanthan gum treatment enhanced the cohesion to 95 kPa for K4S0 and 495 kPa for K1S3. Regarding the friction angle (ϕ'), chitosan produced the greatest increase in both soil types, raising the ϕ' values from 23.76 to 34.58 degrees for K4S0 and from 36.42 to 43.64 degrees for K1S3. Overall, chitosan consistently demonstrated better performance, considerably increasing both shear parameters in both soil types, while carrageenan showed superior effectiveness in fine-graded soil.

4.5. Recommendations for future studies

This study provides an investigation into the use of marine biopolymers for soil treatment applications. There are still several areas still require further research. Some of the most important aspects that require additional research are listed below:

- Evaluate the mechanical behaviour of silt-sand mixtures using additional testing methods, such as direct shear tests or consolidation tests.
- Investigate the long-term performance of biopolymer-treated soils under various environmental variations, such as different temperature and humidity conditions.
- Assess the economic feasibility of marine biopolymers for soil treatment in large-scale projects.
- Explore the compatibility of marine biopolymers with other soil stabilizers and their combined effects on soil performance.
- Investigate the effectiveness of biopolymers in stabilizing soils with varying plasticity or clay content to develop the range of applicable soil types.

5. Conclusions

In this study, the focus was on exploring the potential of chitosan as a promising marine biopolymer for soil improvement. A detailed investigation was conducted to evaluate its effectiveness in enhancing soil strength. The study examined several factors, including biopolymer content, dehydration time, soil type, and durability under wet-dry cycles. Static and dynamic triaxial tests were also conducted to understand the mechanism through which chitosan strengthens the soil. Additionally, a microstructural study using SEM and FTIR provided insights into the interactions between chitosan and soil components. Furthermore, a comprehensive chemical model was developed to elucidate the underlying behaviour of chitosan-treated soil.

This study also investigated the behaviour of chitosan compared with other marine biopolymers, including sodium alginate, agar gum, and carrageenan, and the reference biopolymer xanthan gum, under similar experimental

conditions. Biopolymer content significantly influenced the compressive strength of the treated soil. Chitosan outperformed all other biopolymers across all tested percentages (0.25%, 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5%) and produced the highest increase in soil strength at 1% biopolymer content, increasing the strength by approximately tenfold. The effect of soil type on the biopolymers performance was also studied. Chitosan consistently outperformed in the treatment of soil types, particularly remarkably improving the compressive strength of the K1S3 soil, increasing its strength by more than ninefold. Moreover, the durability of biopolymer-treated soil was evaluated under five cycles of wetting and drying. Chitosan-treated K1S3 demonstrated excellent durability with the least mass loss and the highest retained UCS compared to other biopolymers, indicating strong potential for soil improvement applications.

Microstructural analysis using scanning electron microscopy illustrated insights into the interactions between chitosan and the soil components. Chitosan effectively covered the soil particles and filled the voids, forming hydrogen bonds with kaolinite and hydrophobic interactions with sand. Chitosan/kaolinite composites formed through hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions between chitosan's functional groups and kaolinite's surface hydroxyl groups and uncharged basal surface. For chitosan/sand composites, the dominant interactions were interfacial mechanical interactions resulting from chitosan fibres coating the sand particles and hydrophobic bonding between the polymer chains and sand.

Overall, chitosan cationic nature, strong bonding capacity, balanced hydrophilic–hydrophobic character, and high crosslinking capacity make it a more effective soil stabilizer than carrageenan or other marine biopolymers. These properties contribute to the greater strength improvements observed in chitosan-treated soils, more consistent performance across different soil types, and high durability under wet-dry cycles. Therefore, findings of this study highlights the potential of chitosan as an environmentally compatible marine biopolymer for soil stabilization in geotechnical engineering applications, particularly in countries with abundant marine resources.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Runshen Wang: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Hadi Fatehi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Dominic E.L. Ong:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **Jimmy Yu:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Ilhan Chang:** Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Khosro Shabani:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation.

Funding

This research was supported by “the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities” (B240201026).

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

References

- Afrin, H., 2017. A review on different types soil stabilization techniques. *Int. J. Trans. Eng. Technol.* 3 (2), 19–24.
- Afshar, A., Jahandari, S., Rasekh, H., Shariati, M., Afshar, A., Shokrgozar, A., 2020. Corrosion resistance evaluation of rebars with various primers and coatings in concrete modified with different additives. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 262 120034.
- Almajed, A., Lemboye, K., Arab, M.G., Alnuaim, A., 2020. Mitigating wind erosion of sand using biopolymer-assisted EICP technique. *Soils Found.* 60 (2), 356–371.
- Arab, M.G., Mousa, R., Gabr, A., Azam, A., El-Badawy, S., Hassan, A., 2019. Resilient behavior of sodium alginate-treated cohesive soils for pavement applications. *J. Mater. Civ. Eng.* 31 (1) 04018361.
- ASTM, D. 2006. “Standard test method for unconfined compressive strength of cohesive soil.” ASTM standard D 2166.
- Ayelden, M., Negm, A., El Sawwaf, M., Gädä, T., 2018. Laboratory study of using biopolymer to reduce wind erosion. *Int. J. Geotech. Eng.* 12 (3), 228–240.
- Bahrami, R., Khayat, N., Nazarpour, A., 2020. Effect of nano-stabilizer on geotechnical properties of leached gypsiferous soil. *Geomech. Eng.* 23 (2), 103–113.
- Chang, I., Lee, M., Tran, A.T.P., Lee, S., Kwon, Y.-M., Im, J., Cho, G.-C., 2020. Review on biopolymer-based soil treatment (BPST) technology in geotechnical engineering practices. *Transp. Geotech.* 24 100385.
- D698-12, A. Standard Test Methods for Laboratory Compaction Characteristics of Soil Using Standard Effort (12 400 Ft-lbf/ft³ (600 KN-m/m³)) 1, ASTM international.
- D2850-23, A. Standard Test Method for Unconsolidated-Undrained Triaxial Compression Test on Cohesive Soils. 04.08: 7.
- D4609, A. Standard Guide for Evaluating Effectiveness of Chemicals for Soil Stabilization. 04.08: 5.
- D6913-04, A. 2009. D6913-04, 2009. Standard test methods for particle-size distribution (gradation) of soils using sieve analysis. *Annual Book of ASTM Standards.* 409.
- D6913/D6913M-17, A. 2017. Standard Test Methods for Particle-Size Distribution (Gradation) of Soils Using Sieve Analysis.
- D7181-20, A. Standard Test Method for Consolidated Drained Triaxial Compression Test for Soils. 04.09: 12.
- Fatehi, H., Ong, D.E., Yu, J., Chang, I., 2021. Biopolymers as green binders for soil improvement in geotechnical applications: a review. *Geosciences* 11 (7), 291.
- Fatehi, H., Ong, D.E.L., Yu, J., Chang, I., 2023. The effects of particle size distribution and moisture variation on mechanical strength of biopolymer-treated soil. *Polymers* 15 (6), 1549.
- Fatehi, H., Ong, D.E.L., Yu, J., Chang, I., 2024. Sustainable soil treatment: investigating the efficacy of carrageenan biopolymer on the geotechnical properties of soil. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 411 134627.
- Ghadir, P., Tasuji, M. R. A., Shariatmadari, N., Fatehi, H., Shabani, K. 2022. “Investigation of soil stabilization by cross-linking chitosan and sodium alginate biopolymers.” 20th International Conference on Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering (Sydney).
- Gupta, V., Miller, J.D., 2010. Surface force measurements at the basal planes of ordered kaolinite particles. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 344 (2), 362–371.
- Hamdi, M., Hammami, A., Hajji, S., Jridi, M., Nasri, M., Nasri, R., 2017. Chitin extraction from blue crab (*Portunus segnis*) and shrimp (*Penaeus kerathurus*) shells using digestive alkaline proteases from *P. segnis* viscera. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 101, 455–463.
- Hataf, N., Ghadir, P., Ranjbar, N., 2018. Investigation of soil stabilization using chitosan biopolymer. *J. Clean. Prod.* 170, 1493–1500.
- Izumi, R., Komada, S., Ochi, K., Karasawa, L., Osaki, T., Murahata, Y., Tsuka, T., Imagawa, T., Itoh, N., Okamoto, Y., 2015. Favorable effects of superficially deacetylated chitin nanofibrils on the wound healing process. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 123, 461–467.
- Jafari, A.M., Gharibi, S., Farjadmand, F., Sadighara, P., 2012. Extraction of shrimp waste pigments by enzymatic and alkaline treatment: evaluation by inhibition of lipid peroxidation. *J. Mater. Cycles Waste Manage.* 14 (4), 411–413.
- Kang, X., Bate, B., 2016. Shear wave velocity and its anisotropy of polymer modified high-volume class-F fly ash-kaolinite mixtures. *J. Geotech. Geoenviron. Eng.* 142 (12) 04016068.
- Kang, X., Cao, J., Bate, B., 2020. Shear wave velocity anisotropy of salt-and polymer-amended kaolinite. *Acta Geotech.* 15 (12), 3605–3611.
- Kang, X., Xia, Z., Chen, R., Sun, H., Yang, W., 2019. Effects of inorganic ions, organic polymers, and fly ashes on the sedimentation characteristics of kaolinite suspensions. *Appl. Clay Sci.* 181 105220.
- Kannan, G., Sujatha, E.R., 2023. Crustacean polysaccharides for the geotechnical enhancement of organic silt: a clean and green alternative. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 299 120227.
- Khayat, N., Nasiri, H., 2024. Study of strength characteristics and microstructure analysis of soil stabilized with wastewater and polymer. *Int. J. Pavement Res. Technol.* 17 (5), 1213–1224.
- Kulkarni, V.S., Shaw, C., 2015. *Essential Chemistry for Formulators of Semisolid and Liquid Dosages.* Academic Press.
- Kumar, N., Andersson, M., van den Ende, D., Mugele, F., Siretanu, I., 2017. Probing the surface charge on the basal planes of kaolinite particles with high-resolution atomic force microscopy. *Langmuir* 33 (50), 14226–14237.
- Li, S.-L., He, R.-J., Kang, X., 2023. Permeability of polymer-modified kaolinite and fly ash-kaolinite mixtures. *Géotechnique Letters* 13 (4), 211–217.
- Mehmood, M., Guo, Y., Liu, Y., Wang, L., Nie, W., Uge, B.U., Ali, S., Xuanyu, C., Zhao, Y., 2025. Experimental study on the engineering characteristics of expansive soil improved conjointly using enzyme induced carbonate precipitation and eggshell powder. *Soils Found.* 65 (1) 101567.
- Mirazizi, S., Khayat, N., Nazarpour, A., 2023. Effect of fines content in silt-sand mixtures with different saturations on microbial-induced calcium carbonate precipitation. *Geomicrobiol J.* 40 (3), 227–237.
- Mostafaei, H., Rostampour, M.A., Chamasemani, N.F., Wu, C., 2024. An in-depth exploration of carbon footprint analysis in the construction sector with emphasis on the dam industry. *Carbon Footprint Assessments: Case Studies & Best Practices*, Springer, 45–80.
- Mousa, R., Gabr, A., Arab, M.G., Azam, A., El-Badawy, S., 2017. Resilient modulus for unbound granular materials and subgrade soils in Egypt. *MATEC Web of Conferences* 120, 6009.
- Ni, J., Li, S.-S., Geng, X.-Y., 2022. Mechanical and biodeterioration behaviours of a clayey soil strengthened with combined carrageenan and casein. *Acta Geotech.* 17 (12), 5411–5427.
- Niaounakis, M. 2015. *Biopolymers: applications and trends*, William Andrew.
- Ohadian, A., Khayat, N., Mokhberi, M., 2024a. Microstructural analysis of marl stabilized with municipal solid waste and nano-MgO. *J. Rock Mech. Geotech. Eng.* 16 (8), 3258–3269.
- Ohadian, A., Khayat, N., Mokhberi, M., Horpibulsuk, S., 2024b. Soft clay modified with municipal solid waste and stabilized with nano-MgO for pavement subgrade and embankment fill applications. *Transp. Geotech.* 46 101261.
- Rasheed, R.M., Moghal, A.A.B., Basha, B.M., Almajed, A., 2025. Effect of chitosan and casein on the CBR behavior of silty clay for low volume roads: reliability-based design optimization approach. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 473 141014.

- Reddy, J.J., Varaprasad, B., 2021. Long-term and durability properties of xanthan gum treated dispersive soils—an eco-friendly material. *Mater. Today Proc.* 44, 309–314.
- Samad, A., Mohamad, N., Tambichik, M., Bosro, M., Goli, M., 2021. Strength properties of green concrete mix with added palm oil fibre and its application as a load-bearing hollow block. In: *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, IOP Publishing.
- Santa, B., 1994. Resilient modulus of subgrade soils: Comparison of two constitutive equations. *Transp. Res. Rec.* 1462, 79–90.
- Shabani, K., Bahmani, M., Fatehi, H., Chang, I., 2022. Improvement of the geotechnical engineering properties of dune sand using a plant-based biopolymer named serish. *Geomech. Eng.* 29 (5), 535–548.
- Shariatmadari, N., Reza, M., Tasuji, A., Ghadir, P., Javadi, A.A., 2020. Experimental study on the effect of chitosan biopolymer on sandy soil stabilization. *E3S Web of Conferences*, EDP Sciences.
- Smitha, S., Rangaswamy, K., Keerthi, D., 2019. Triaxial test behaviour of silty sands treated with agar biopolymer. *Int. J. Geotech. Eng.*, 1–12.
- Smitha, S., Rangaswamy, K., Keerthi, D., 2021. Triaxial test behaviour of silty sands treated with agar biopolymer. *Int. J. Geotech. Eng.* 15 (4), 484–495.
- Sujatha, E.R., Saisree, S., 2019. Geotechnical behaviour of guar gum-treated soil. *Soils Found.* 59 (6), 2155–2166.
- Wang, R., Ong, D.E., Sadighi, H., Goli, M., Xia, P., Fatehi, H., Yao, T., 2025. Optimizing soil stabilization with chitosan: investigating acid concentration, temperature, and long-term strength. *Polymers* 17 (2), 151.